

PARENTING OF GENERATION Z WITH GENERATION ALPHA CHILDREN: A CASE STUDY

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Parenting of Generation Z with Generation Alpha Children: A Case Study

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Abstract

This study explored how parenting may be described by Generation Z parents in parenting their Generation Alpha children. It explored the challenges and coping strategies of three resident Generation Z married couples in the City of Koronadal, South Cotabato, who have Generation Alpha children. This research featured a qualitative case study method, specifically a single case approach, as it aimed to provide an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon within the case boundaries, which is a rigorous, transferrable understanding of the phenomenon. The results revealed that lenient, adaptive, and empathic approaches were the major characteristics that described Generation Z parenting. Meanwhile, problems with parenting, screen time discipline, guidance and discipline, and economic hardship were all issues that Generation Z parents dealt with. To cope, parents of Generation Z used techniques including valuing physical, social interaction, seeking solace in prayer and optimism, being adept at time management, adjusting through parental adaptation, and coming to terms with responsible parenting. Ultimately, the results offer a glance into the varied elements of Generation Z parenting, addressing both their parenting and the challenges they encounter, along with their helpful coping mechanisms.

Keywords: *parenting, Generation Z, Generation Alpha*

Introduction

Parenting is not just a responsibility but also a duty that requires sufficient time, love, and study to ensure a good future for one's child. Members of Generation Z, also known as iGen or centennials, were born in 1997-2012. Interestingly, a sizable proportion of Generation Z choose to postpone having children until later in life than prior generations, with some intentionally choosing not to have them at all. This is not a hasty decision, but rather a reflection of the society they have grown up in, which is fraught with economic uncertainty, societal change, and technological revolution. It also demonstrates their desire for control over reproductive decisions and to have children, if at all, on their own terms also Generation Z thinks and behaves in new ways, aspires to new ideas, and pursues them through new means of reimagining parenting. As new generations emerge, such as the Generation Alpha, the most recent batch studies are being conducted because Alphas will be navigating an increasingly complex and fast changing world, confronting global challenges, and forging careers in businesses that do not yet exist. Alphas will require confidence in their own capacity to consistently improve and cultivate their skill set while retaining an attitude of curiosity and invention to flourish as they grow (Hosid, 2021).

For Generation Z, having children is the primary source of determination, purpose, and fulfilment. According to the study of We, The Family (2021), Generation Z parent view their child as a complement to their identity that enhances their personality rather than a compromise. As parents, they have a sense of responsibility, which makes them good decision-makers. As a result of their own childhood experiences with technology acting as a babysitter, Generation Z parents prioritize sharing experiences with their children. They are aware of the potential negative consequences of technology and social media, such as a lack of individualized social interaction. They are more likely to adapt their own and their children's use of technology to mitigate these negative effects, but they may find it difficult to form relationships without online connections. Crowdsourcing their vast social networks and obtaining information from sources that correspond with their experiences and values, Gen Z members form opinions. They rely significantly on social media for news and information and so much of what they consume may be unvetted. Generation Z parents also encourage their children to adapt through changes in work, fashion, mental health, social media, and they adapt their approaches to parenting (Chaney & Waters, 2021).

Meanwhile, Filipino families have changed dramatically over the last ten years, and their children's learning is increasingly shifting toward a broader vision of 21st-century learning (Bartolome et al., 2017). Traditionally, Filipino families have made decisions for their kids. Elders frequently tell their grandchildren they want them to become doctors, lawyers, or engineers out of personal preference (Santos, 2022). In turn, children see academic success as a way to live up to their parent's expectations and fulfill their duties as filial children.

In a study conducted in Tacurong, Sultan Kudarat about Permissive Parenting Style and Maladaptive Behavioral Tendencies Among Junior High School Students of Notre Dame of Tacurong College, Mindanao, Philippines by Cabanatuan and Ahmad (2021) it was found that parents are most likely to have a positive attitude toward their children more likely the Generation Z parents place more excellent value on giving autonomy to their children than the previous generation of parents, such as parents from Generation X and Boomers. The study conducted by Silvano (2019) also stated that there is an influence between the behaviors of parents in rearing a child and the life satisfaction of parents in SOCCSKSARGEN.

As a result, parenting has a significant impact on the lives of the children. The parents' influence can help create emotional and psychological challenges that will help in rearing the new generation.

Parents are expected to play an extremely important role in their child's growth. The new generation of parents, known as Generation Z, faces the challenge of navigating a world where technology is more prevalent. As a result, they developed new approaches to parenting the emerging Generation Alpha. With Generation Alpha's easy access to the internet, they tend to spend more time in front of screens, which can lead to hyperactive behaviors.

Therefore, it is important to understand the parenting by the new generation of parents towards their Generation Alpha children, especially considering the pervasive influence of existing technology. Understanding the new approaches, difficulties, and adaptations made by these parents shape their parenting choices in the light of technological advancement in raising Generation Alpha children. This could provide invaluable insights for researchers and practitioners in the fields of child development, family studies, and digital technology in the societal landscape.

Research Questions

This study described the parenting of Generation Z Parents with their Generation Alpha Children. Specifically, this answered the following:

1. How may Parenting of Generation Z parents with Generation Alpha children be described?
2. What are the challenges of Generation Z parents in parenting their Generation Alpha children?
3. What are the coping strategies of Generation Z parents in parenting their Generation Alpha children?

Literature Review

Parenting

Parenting is doing anything for the child to become like a human being. Parenting is the primary responsibility of parents, and it includes meeting the child's basic needs, practicing the most basic life skills, meeting the child's needs for materials, meeting the child's emotional and psychological requirements (Cahapay, 2021), moreover, as stated by Fatyimah (2021), parenting is providing the opportunity for children to receive a proper education as part of basic responsibility brought by being a parent.

The study conducted by Jha (2020) in the study entitled parenting Generation Alpha, stated that effective parenting is seen in the first two years of the children, which are critical for the healthy development in attachment and relationships. As it is found that Generation Alpha is centered with technological advancement. As a result, the current parenting pattern appears to be polarized, with excessive love, affection, and continual monitoring of the child on the one hand and hiring babysitters and caregivers when they are out.

Moreover, as suggested by the study of Novianti et al. (2019), smart parenting can benefit children in reaching their full potential by enhancing their ability to learn and aiding them in becoming skilled and thriving persons as it is not attempting to control the move of children but it is teaching and guiding them along the way. Parents that practice smart parenting understand their children's requirements and use suitable ways to help them flourish. This could include emotional support, engaging learning experiences, and hands-on activities that help youngsters improve their skills (Hasanah et al., 2022).

Psychologists have long emphasized the importance of family processes in child development (Talib et al., 2011). Parents with parent-child interaction, parent-child joint activities, and parental involvement in children's education are important in socialization and children's functioning. They built better connections than those parents who are always away and do not attend the child's activity. It allows children to express their thoughts, form their own opinions, and make their judgments. However, as a result in the study of Cabanatuan and Ahmad (2022) having interaction with children like in permissive parenting does not help in developing their maladaptive behavior tendencies due to low demands of children but high responsiveness from parents.

The importance of parenting is particularly highlighted in Philippine society, in which the family is generally seen as central to one's social world (Alampay, 2019). According to Alampay (2019), the Filipino family is defined by its cohesiveness, respect for elders, obedience to parental authority, and fulfilment of mutual commitments. However, the social context in which Filipino families live has altered significantly in the last 10 years, potentially influencing how parents and children think about and respond to one another. These changes result in modifications in parenting ideas and practices, such as a move from authoritarian to more liberal or autonomous parenting attitudes. As a result of generational differences, parents have to adapt and avoid the bad experiences with parenting styles they experience in their own childhood.

Generation Z

Generation Z refers to people born between 1997 and 2012. Generation Z was the first generation born into a globally connected world and therefore "live and breathe" technology. Rothman (2016) illustrated that the brains of Generation Z are structurally different from those of earlier generations, not as a result of genetics, but as a result of the external environment and how our brains respond. As stated by Rothman (2016) "The brains of Generation Zs have become wired to sophisticated, complex visual imagery, and as a result, the part of the brain responsible for visual ability is far more developed, making visual forms of learning more effective". Auditory learning, such as lectures and discussions, is very strongly disliked by this group, whereas interactive games, collaborative projects, advanced organizers, and challenges are appreciated.

The emergence of technology tested the usage of Generation Z in the study of Bermudez et al. (2020), wherein Generation Z uses technology to make creative outputs online to provide information about their life and post in their social media. Social media is widely used in society and is used by people to share information about the news, enabling them to reach a larger audience. Generation Z today also uses social media to communicate with their family and friends to share what is happening to them on a real time basis (Olipas, 2022). One of the factors that shapes generations is technology, particularly the quick change in how people interact and communicate (Dimock, 2019).

Generation Alpha

The arrival of a new generation occurred where social media developed. A generational researcher, Mark McCrindle, coined the phrase, Generation Alpha. According to Jha (2020), Generation Alpha is named after the first letter of the Greek alphabet, Alpha. Members of this generation were born in 2010-2024 and their immediate predecessors, Generation Zs mark the end of Latin alphabets in the series of naming generations, paving way for the Gen Alpha to emerge. This is the new generation that will soon fill classrooms and universities and demand unique approaches to teaching learning, based on their unique skill sets and requirements (Ziatdinov & Cilliers, 2021). Generation Alpha members are living in a different technological driven reality, which may wreak havoc on their future life (Jha, 2020).

According to Ziatdinov and Cilliers (2021), Generation Alpha has been labeled as generation glass, screenagers, digital natives, and the connected or wired generation because of their clear connection to technology and technological innovation. Being born in a highly digitalized world ultimately gives them an advantage, in engaging with the primary machinery that society has today, found in the form of hand-held gadgets, used in entertainment (Ziatdinov & Cilliers, 2021), gaming, connecting to peers, and education in the wake of COVID-19 pandemic. Thus, their life revolves around technology (Jha & Arora, 2020).

Generation Alpha, who are currently dealing with an array of technological challenges, should be trained to liberate themselves from their servitude. While witnessing the profound human–technology integration in daily life, Jha et al. (2019) argues for a healthy and integrated approach, where both can be assimilated, for technology to stay and play the role of a great redeemer rather than a foe to mankind.

Generation Z as Parents

Generation Z views parenthood as their new layer of identity. According to We the Family (2019), They believe being a parent is a compliment not a compromise to their existence and it enhances their existing personalities which makes their life better. Additionally, Generation Z has different ideas of being a parent compared to the millennial parent who focuses on work ethic and earning an income, according to Picard, 2023. She elaborates that Generation Z parents are reaching for perfection as they put emphasis on being a perfect parent. They strive to reach parenting ideals from keeping their children busy with activities, ensuring technology-free time, being open to children, prioritizing family, and adapting easily to setbacks and difficulties.

Turning to their devices for quick answers and guidance is one of the characteristics of a Generation Z parent. They look for materials like blog posts, videos, or infographics, that provide immediate value and answers to their questions to learn and adapt quickly (Jolasun, 2023). As a result, they are more aware of the potential adverse effects of technology and social media compared to previous generations like Gen X and Millennials (Waters & Chaney, 2021). They are likely to adjust their own and their children's technology usage to mitigate these negative impacts.

Being a Generation Z parent ensures a Work-life balance. It is a significant priority for them to have flexible employment options to accommodate the parenting responsibilities (IBM Institute for Business Value, 2020). They have the urge to attend to both the physiological and emotional needs of their generation alpha children.

Most parents experience parenting difficulties and the majority of the reason is that school events take place during the working day, making it difficult for parents who have jobs to attend them all. Some people can perceive this as a failure, particularly mothers (Meyer, 2018). Moreover, Generation Z parents have difficulties with time management, roles and obligations, personal and economic support, and parenting experiences. The problems stem from the various duties that they must undertake all by themselves while still managing time to accomplish their concurrent responsibilities. They must become acquainted with their new roles and obligations as parents; they require assistance to complete all personal or parental activities, and their lack of parenting experience makes it difficult for them to manage these duties and responsibilities (Ebor, 2022).

Additionally, for some parents, this is a major concern because it contradicts their approach to parenting. It is common for parents to have idealistic expectations for their children and to become disappointed when those expectations are not realized. With the existence of technology changed the way children learn, enjoy themselves, and connect with others in society. Younger children spend most of their time on their phones, laptops, and other technology that have both beneficial and harmful effects on their life. The internet, technology, social media, and online gaming are driving the new generation deranged, making them addicted to them.

A potential problem with parenting in the technologically advanced generation, according to Davies (2020), is the lack of distinction between strong bonds, like those with real–life friends and family, and weak ones, like those with online–only friends and casual acquaintances. This comes with significant obligations and challenges for parents, particularly Generation Z women, in safeguarding

and protecting their children from internet hazards. Technology has provided various tools to assist parents execute their parenting responsibilities of educating and entertaining their children, but it has also made their parenting more complex (Jimenez, Lazaro, Sison, Soniega, & Barrera, 2016).

Generation Z Parents Coping Strategies

Coping Mechanisms are any conscious or unconscious adjustment or adaptation that reduces tension and anxiety in a stressful experience or situation according to the American Psychological Association (2014). The goal of psychological treatments is frequently to modify dysfunctional coping mechanisms.

In the study of Vice Media Group (2021) Generation Z does not see parenthood as a hindrance, rather, they view it as a source of inspiration to strive for excellence in life, driven by their desire to provide for their families. This suggests that for Generation Z, their family serves as a coping mechanism during times of stress, as they channel their energy and motivation towards creating a better life for their loved ones. As they are the new set of parents in this generation, Generation Z parents find it stressful to learn the complexities of raising a child. However, they have the advantage of receiving advice from previous generations on parenting techniques. Despite this guidance, Generation Z parents often choose to rely on their own instincts when it comes to making decisions for their children.

According to Brown (2020) Generation Z parents demonstrate a higher tendency to seek assistance from mental health professionals when experiencing stress. Generation Z is more aware of mental health difficulties than prior generations that is why mental health clinics are becoming more widely available in cities. This inclination arises from their heightened awareness and mindfulness regarding mental health issues. Seeking help from mental health professionals is seen as a proactive coping strategy among Generation Z parents, reflecting their commitment to managing stress and promoting their overall well-being.

Methodology

Participants

This research aimed to involve parents belonging to Generation Z who are residents of Koronadal City and have children in the age range of 5 to 11. The eligible participants be 18 to 26 which falls under Generation Z parents and they should be married to further share insights about the experience of raising generation alpha child in building a family. These participants were selected based on these criteria, and subsequently, three Generation Z parents with Generation Alpha children were chosen for in-depth interviews, following the submission of an Informed Consent Letter. By concentrating on Generation Z parents in this specific city, this study provided valuable insights into their unique experiences, perspectives, and parenting practices when it comes to raising Generation Alpha children.

CASE 1: PARTICIPANT 1 is a married couple, the persons who make up the pair are both 23 years old, residing in Barangay Namnama, City of Koronadal, South Cotabato. The couple has 2 children, aged 5 and 3. They had their first born when they were in Senior high school and they were still both students at that time. They were both raised in a religious family and their parents decided to let them be married at the age of 18. They are now both third year students, still living under the same roof with the husband's family. The interview was held in the afternoon on November 23, 2023 in Cafe Bistro. Both of them are welcoming and demonstrate willingness to share their experiences on having a Generation Alpha child.

CASE 2: PARTICIPANT 2 consists of a married couple, aged 22 and 26, residing in Brgy. Zone IV, City of Koronadal, South Cotabato. The couple shares a household with the husband's family and has a one 5-year-old daughter. The male participant works as a security guard, while the female participant is currently in her third year of college. The interview took place in Mug Wagi, where they expressed their openness to cooperate and shared valuable parenting experiences related to their Generation Alpha child.

CASE 3: PARTICIPANT 3 is a married couple. The persons who make up the pair are both 25 years old, living in Brgy. Sta. Cruz, City of Koronadal, South Cotabato. They have 3 children, 2 boys and one girl. Their eldest is 7 years old, next is 5, and the youngest is 3 years old. They had their first born when they were 18 years old, studying as third year college students. A year after delivering their first child they decided to get married. The male participant is now a farmer and the female participant is now a clerk. The interview was held in the afternoon on December 20, 2023 at the couple's residence. They were warm and welcoming and showed willingness to participate in the conduct of the study. They shared fruitful information about their experiences in parenting their Generation Alpha children.

Instruments

The researchers used semi-structured interviews to have an in-depth interview with the Generation Z parent participants about their experiences in parenting Generation Alpha children. The instrument is designed to encourage open-ended responses from the respondents, who are Generation Z parents of Generation Alpha children. The interview included a general set of guide questions to direct the interview process, such as an easily understood set of guide questions that are supported by additional follow-up questions and exploratory questions based on the interviewee's responses, allowing participants to introduce fresh ideas and share personal experiences through their interview.

Furthermore, the questions were validated by an experienced and knowledgeable professor. Thus, the researchers will use this type of interview to have an essential and detailed understanding on the experiences of Generation Z parents in parenting the Generation Alpha children.

The research questions were carefully crafted to cover relevant topics such as describing Generation Z parenting, challenges in parenting Generation Alpha, coping strategies of Generation Z parents and the experiences of Generation Z parents. Probing questions were also included to further clarify and expand on the responses given by the respondents. The interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatimly with the consent of the participants.

The collected data were analyzed using a thematic analysis approach. The final version of the research instrument was used in the data collection phase of the study to ensure that the data collected was reliable and valid. The confidentiality of the participants was to be maintained throughout the study, and the findings of the study would be shared with the participants if appropriate.

Procedure

The researcher followed a step-by-step procedure in conducting and gathering data from the participants. In order to acquire relevant and important information in the study, the process followed is provided below:

First, the researchers obtained the approval of the college dean of the College of Arts and Sciences (CAS) and the research adviser. Its objective is to ensure that the study is carried out in a way that preserves the researchers' rights, dignity, and safety. Once the study is approved, the researchers sought for participants based on the inclusion criteria of the study.

Second, the researchers obtained consent from the participants through an informed consent letter stating whether they have the right to participate or not in the study. The researchers explained the nature of the study and the rights and roles of participants during the interview.

Lastly, the researcher started the data gathering. The interview was conducted with the permission of the participants to record the conversation through audio recording and writing notes. The researcher utilized the Interview Guide Question provided that it is semi-structured and approved by the adviser and the college dean. The researchers gave ample time for the participants to elaborate on their answers to obtain an in-depth perspective and ideas on the parents' Generation Z parenting on their Generation Alpha children. The interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim with the consent of the participants.

The collected data were analyzed using a thematic analysis approach. The data gathered, and the recorded sessions of the interviewed were stored in a file on a fellow researcher's device, and there were copies of the recorded sessions in another device in case of an emergency.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are critical in research to ensure that participants' rights and well-being remain secure and that the research is carried out with honesty and rigor. The researcher followed an interview protocol before conducting the interviews.

A letter to conduct individual interviews will be approved and signed by the research adviser, moderator, and the college dean of the College of Arts and Sciences. A letter of consent was also given to the study participants. An informed consent containing the rights of participants to accept or refuse to be interviewed by the researcher was also provided.

Another ethical aspect in research is respecting participants' confidentiality and privacy contributed to the development of trust between researchers and participants while also protecting participants' right to privacy and secrecy. Maintaining participant anonymity and privacy, informed consent, and confidentiality was utilized, which involved reducing risks and optimizing advantages for participants, ensuring fairness and equity in participant selection, conducting research with scientific integrity and transparency, and addressing conflicts of interest. The researchers preserved the participants' privacy and confidentiality by anonymizing data, employing secure storage and transmission protocols, and gaining participant consent for sharing of information or publication. If there is an opportunity to publish the paper virtually or physically, the researcher will ensure that the participants will be formally informed and have access of their data. The researcher will ensure that the study will be shared broadly with the participant's permission as they contributed the result of this study.

Results and Discussion

This section systematically presents the findings obtained from interviews with Generation Z parents, and the analysis of their parenting practices for a Generation Alpha child. The exploration delves into dissecting specific characteristics and beliefs that play a pivotal role in shaping their parenting.

SOP1: Parenting of Generation Z with Generation Alpha children

The presented table shows the themes that emerged from the significant statements and formulated meanings of the participants about the parenting of Generation Z with generation alpha children.

Table 1. Thematic analysis on how may parenting of Generation Z Parents with Generation Alpha Children

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme
PARTICIPANT 1		Lenient
<i>MOTHER: "sa pag discipline... ako abi dali lang abi ko mahurt, ng basta ano basta may ara siya ano. Kung ako ginahambalan ko lang na siya kung ano mga possibility nga mga matabo liwat."</i>	Indicating a reluctance to easily resort to punitive measures	Adaptive
<i>"Ginahambalan ko na siya, 'sige kung gusto na nga maliwat na', di na paghimua, ng way nga gina hambalan ko lang siya"</i>	Communicate in gentle manner to educate	Empathetic
<i>FATHER: "Same lang"</i>		
<i>MOTHER: "sakon abi kay bal an niya nga daw soft ko, gina lambing lambing ko siya nga okay lang sa iya kay kung papa niya nahadlok na siya"</i>	Caring approach Establish socialization	
<i>FATHER: "tapos gachurch kami tapos sina ga ano kami galagaw lagaw kami sa KCC, magkaon pero ang pinakaginahimo gid namon maghampang."</i>	Set quality time	
<i>MOTHER: "gahatag gid ko sa time ko gd nga para sa bata ko nga maghampang kami nga tatlo"</i>		
PARTICIPANT 2		
<i>MOTHER: "sakon as nanay gn padako ko gd siya nga may kahadlok bala saamon nga parents niya"</i>	Set authority	
<i>FATHER: "ga kayod sako para saiya gyapon...para maka tapon nga pagdako niya may ara gd siya nga..."</i>	Eager in earning	
<i>MOTHER: "as a parent ako ang hindi klase sang parent nga i-spoiled ko ang bata ko"</i>	Type of parent to not indulge or overly pamper their child	
<i>MOTHER: "ga react... si (name) abi ky tipo sng bata nga kung ano kailangan hindi mo siya isinggitan hindi mo siya idalon sa akig ka ng siya ang tipo sang bata nga paintindihon mo siya sa mahinay hinay na storya"</i>	Emphasizes the effectiveness of calmly explaining things to the child through gentle conversation	
<i>FATHER: "kung kisa hindi siya ma control kay gusto, gusto niya gid..."</i>	Provides everything and indulges the child's desires	
<i>MOTHER: "ga pati siya ky papa niya ky gna hatag tanan... ky gina pagustohan"</i>		
<i>MOTHER: "close close gid kami sang bata ko ky kwan ng hindi... hindi niya gani kaya kung kisa nga wala kami"</i>	Strong attachment Strong commitment to family time	
<i>"Hindi siya makatulog mo kung wala ko sa kilid niya"</i>		
<i>"Baga hindi ko lang siya bata dw naging manghod ko siya, bestfriend ko na, amo na na kmi nga duwa"</i>		
<i>FATHER: "ah sobra ka ano eh... kung sa close... close gd ky mag abot ko sa trabaho... tulog pa na siya ga bugtaw... basta mag gahod ang motor ko ah"</i>	Prioritizing experiences on creating enjoyable moments	
<i>MOTHER: "pag abot sa storyahan na family time, biskan ano pa rason nga amo ni, may emergency, oh ano sa trabaho mas... lalo na pag ano Sunday kay amo gd abi ng time nga complete kmi mas gahatag gd kami sang panahon sa isa kag isa"</i>	Attentive and responsive to the child's preference	
<i>"kahit ano lang ng kwarta namon kahit hindi sang damo pero mas gina pili namon mag kaon sa gawas, malakat kmi sa Jollibee gna dala namon siya sa Jollibee ky amo man ng paborito niya nga ano... nga ano restaurant, ay fast food gli"</i>		

<p><i>“biskan ano ka pigado or ano gahatag gd kmi sang way nga ma ano namon siya... ma enjoy niya nga upod niya kami”</i></p>	<p>Indulges their children and Allocate time for them to use gadget</p>
<p><i>MOTHER: “may time man nga gusto niya basahan siya sang ano... ng sugid sugidan mo bala siyang story hw”</i></p>	<p>Influences and interaction at school</p>
<p><i>“basta storyahon mo lang siya nga storyahon taga kagabi, matulogan man lang na siya”</i></p>	<p>Prioritizes physical activities</p>
<p><i>MOTHER: “as a ginikanan niya ti may times gd nga gina tagaan sang panahon nga mag gadget, kung mag-abot kami, excited gd na siya ky balan niya nga pagustohan siya namon mo, kami lang ang maka hatag sang tablet saiya”</i></p>	<p>Adapting to circumstances and using available resources for the child</p>
<p><i>FATHER: ang mga bata subong ga dako, lain dati nga mga nga nahadlok sa ginikanan subong lain na abi subong ang pamalakad sang mga kabataan ky gamay lang nga may makita nga kwan... sa tanan na bata sa school, ky mahimo nila</i></p>	<p>Forming a relationship with child despite absence of parental figures</p>
<p><i>MOTHER: sila na ni papa niya, more on sa mga physical activities</i></p>	<p>Belief that learning comes first in the household</p>
<p><i>“sakon abi ky mahilig ko mag bakal sang mga drawing book mga water book niya mga amo balan na hw, ti hindi mn ko ka ano, hindi man ko kalakat, hindi ko kagawas dyun (ky may ubrahon pa sa sulod balay) kaya ang style ko para hindi mag ano mag sigi ka gadget amo na gna hatag ko saiya”</i></p>	<p>Giving importance to bonding during the early years of the child</p>
<p><i>MOTHER: sa akon nga nag dako nga waay sang parent noh ng kumbaga naga buo ka sang relationship mo saimo nga bata</i></p>	
<p><i>“ky dba tuod gd mn nga ang education ky ga start gd sa balay, amo gd ng gina patihan ko nga learning kg ang education naga umpisa gd sa balay hindi sa school”</i></p>	
<p><i>FATHER: mag dako nga daad sya ti sbng mo lang siya nga mabonding nga gamay pa siya ky kung mag dako na siya, wala na.. hindi kana ka kwan saiya ky ti... lain gd kung bata pa</i></p>	
<p>Participant 3</p>	
<p><i>FATHER: “gapaningkamot”</i> <i>“para nga ihatag sa ila tanan kung ano ang gusto nila, kag gapaningkamot man para maihatag sa ila tanan ang kung ang ano wala nakon nga nakuha sa nga ginikanan sang una. Di ko man gusto nga ma ano ng, ano hindi ko mahatag sa ila.”</i></p>	<p>Keeness in having the best for their child</p>
<p><i>FATHER: “Ginpadako ko na sila as a papa nga may kahadlok sila saakon, tanan na sila tatlo basta ako hadlok na sila pero kung time na nga ako ang maghatag sa ila tanan nga needs kag wants nila ihatag ko gid kag kung pangayuon ginahatag ko gid”</i></p>	<p>Instilling a sense of apprehension</p>
<p><i>MOTHER: “di [ko] gusto nga kis-a abi masubrahan niya abi na kapaspoil ang mga bata, ti ako ako gapugong nga indi pagbakli amo na.”</i></p>	<p>Inculcate sense of restrain</p>
<p><i>FATHER: ang pagreact sang bata saakon wala man ko may nakita nga negative reaction nila kay tungod nga biskan gapangaktig ko sa ila pero kung ano gusto nila mahatag ko man kag ginapaningkamotan ko man ngaihatag ko kung ano gusto nila.</i> <i>ga lambingon naton ibaklan kung ano gusto nila para nga wala sila may ihambal nga malain saaton or negative saaton para saakon lang.</i></p>	<p>Proactively responding to the child’s desires</p>
<p><i>MOTHER: saakon, makita mo man nga ano sila ang ila nga maglambing sa imo, pero kis’a may ara gid nga ano ang bata bay nga maghibi sila, tung ikaduwa namon aga pa magtantrum gid siya, mahibi tapos pero amo lang na eh isturyahon ti lambingon niyo nman siya makahipos abi sa ano mga bata.</i></p>	<p>Attuned to the nuances of their child’s behavior</p>
<p><i>FATHER: “parehas sina ng tatlo namon ka bata mahilig na sa 7/11, paghibi na grabe na maghibi hmban mo lang sila nga maadto sa 7/11 okay na na. magbihis na para madkadto nata sa 7/11. Wala na na ga dugang pa di na na maghibi daw amo ng ila nga ano.”</i></p>	<p>Promptly fulfilling the child’s request</p>
<p><i>MOTHER: “kung akigan mo magdugang ila hibi tapos daw maakig sa imo magsunggod”</i></p>	<p>Thoughtful and considerate handling of communication and discipline</p>
	<p>Prioritization of family bonding</p>

FATHER: “para sakon maka bonding kami kung may ara kami nga occasions maadto kami didto”
“Bonding bonding, amo na malipay man ang mga bata , kag ang mga bata daw. kung sa ano pa, gapangita gyapon sila sang ginikanan, mama kag papa gid.”

Fostering an unwavering emotional bond and understanding

FATHER: “ang bata maski layo sila wala namon na feel nga...layo ang ila feelings sa amon pag abot na sa ila pero ginapangita nila gyapon kami”

MOTHER: daw mag abot sila diri mapalambing sila mahug hug

FATHER: “mag abot sila diri gapanghita gid sila sang papa kag mama nga tuod gid nga pagpalangga lain gid ila nga ano saamon.”

MOTHER: Mag uli sila diri indi nila gusto nga magbalik na daw amo sina.

Lenient

Generation Z parents often exhibit a lenient approach to parenting, characterized by a tolerant and relaxed attitude towards discipline. In contrast to rigid schedules and strict rules, they prioritize their children's enjoyment of childhood and encourage exploration of new experiences (Kibin, 2024). Generation Z parents resonate with the principles of the Parent Development Theory. This theory underscores the idea that parental perspectives evolve over time, reflecting societal changes and cultural shifts. Generation Z parents, having grown up in a dynamic and rapidly changing world themselves, tend to adopt a more relaxed and flexible approach to parenting compared to previous generations. They prioritize fostering independence and exploration in their children, valuing experiences over rigid rules and schedules. This leniency reflects their belief in allowing their children the freedom to navigate and learn from their surroundings, while also recognizing the importance of providing guidance and support along the way.

P1 emphasizes fostering communication in a gentle manner, *Ginahambalan ko na siya, ‘sige kung gusto na nga maliwat na’, di na paghimua, ng way nga gina hambalan ko lang siya*

P2 expresses a similar sentiment, *ga react... si (name) abi ky tipo sang bata nga kung ano kailangan hindi mo siya isinggitan hindi mo siya idalon sa akig ka ng siya ang tipo sang bata nga paintindihon mo siya sa mahinay hinay na storya*

P3 advocates for handling situations thoughtfully, wherein P3 stated this, *saakon, makita mo man nga ano sila ang ila nga maglambing sa imo, pero kis’a may ara gid nga ano ang bata bay nga maghibi sila, tung ikaduwa namon aga pa magtantrum gid siya, mahibi tapos pero amo lang na eh isturyahon ti lambingon niyo nman siya makahipon abi sa ano mga bata, kung akigan mo magdugang ila hibi tapos daw maakig sa imo magsunggod*

These statements are considered lenient because they reflect an attitude of tolerance, patience, and understanding in communication and conflict resolution.

The Participants convey a shared perspective of cultivating a sense of respect and apprehension in their parenting.

As regards this, P2 articulates the following, *sakon as nanay gn padako ko gd siya nga may kahadlok bala saamon nga parents niya*

Similarly, P3 stated this, *Ginpadako ko na sila as a papa nga may kahadlok sila saakon, tanan na sila tatlo basta ako hadlok na sila pero kung time na nga ako ang maghatag sa ila tanan nga needs kag wants nila ihatag ko gid kag kung pangayuon ginahatag ko gid*

Leniency is apparent as the participants aim to instill respect without resorting to overly strict or authoritarian measures, recognizing the importance of a balanced and understanding parental approach.

The mothers of the participants employ a distinctive parenting approach characterized by their tendency not to indulge or overly pamper their children. Rather than fostering excessive indulgence, they prioritize instilling a sense of restraint and moderation in their children's needs. This nuanced approach suggests a deliberate effort to balance care and boundaries, promoting responsible behavior and a healthy understanding of limits within their children.

P2 expresses this perspective by stating, *“as a parent ako ang hindi klase sang parent nga i-spoiled ko ang bata ko”*

Similarly, P3 articulates: *“di [ko] gusto nga kis-a abi masubrahan niya abi na kapaspoil ang mga bata, ti ako ako ga-pugong nga indi pagbakli amo na.*

Both participants affirm the shared sentiment of avoiding overindulgence, showcasing a deliberate commitment to promoting responsible behavior and maintaining healthy boundaries within their parenting approach. The leniency lies in the measured and thoughtful approach to parenting that prioritizes responsible behavior without resorting to excessive pampering or permissiveness.

The participant fathers strive to fulfill all of their children's needs, indulging their desires and proactively responding to their wishes.

In which P2 stated that “*kung kisa hindi siya ma control kay gusto, gusto niya gid...*” and the Mother concurs, stating that, “*ga pati siya ky papa niya ky gna hatag tanan... ky gina pagustohan*”

As for P3, the following was stated, *ang pagreact sang bata saakon wala man ko may nakita nga negative reaction nila kay tungod nga biskan gapangkig ko sa ila pero kung ano gusto nila mahatag ko man kag ginapaningkamotan ko man ngaihatag ko kung ano gusto nila., ga lambingon naton ibaklan kung ano gusto nila para nga wala sila may ihambal nga malain saaton or negative saaton para saakon lang.*

The participant goes to great lengths to meet their children's wishes, purchasing items they desire. This active engagement is motivated by a desire to preempt any negative comments or feelings from the children, emphasizing the importance of maintaining a positive and amicable relationship within the family. The approach underscores a commitment to understanding and meeting the emotional needs of the children, fostering an environment of mutual respect and contentment. This leniency lies in the fathers' flexibility and willingness to accommodate the children's preferences, creating an environment where the children's desires are acknowledged and often met without strict constraints or resistance.

Parent Development Theory, which posits that parents evolve in their perspectives over time, can be seen in the participants' commitment to adapting their parenting styles. For example, P3's approach of not seeing negative reactions from the children even when expressing frustration indicates a dynamic and evolving parent-child connection. This aligns with Parent Development Theory, suggesting an evolving parental perspective aimed at nurturing a positive and flexible parent-child dynamic

Adaptive

Generation Z parents demonstrate adaptability in their parenting approach, which involves integrating traditional values with a contemporary understanding of their children's diverse needs. This adaptability allows them to navigate various situations effectively while accommodating the evolving dynamics of parenting in today's world.

P1 stated the following, *tapos gachurch kami tapos sina ga ano kami galagaw lagaw kami sa KCC, magkaon pero ang pinakaginahimo gid namon maghampang, gahatag gid ko sa time ko gd nga para sa bata ko nga maghampang kami nga tatlo*

Despite their busy schedule, the participant emphasized allocating quality time specifically for their child, highlighting the importance of bonding through play. It also suggests a strong commitment to dedicating personal time for the child, reinforcing the significance of meaningful interactions within the family.

P2 also mentions the following, *kahit ano lang ng kwarta namon kahit hindi sang damo pero mas gina pili namon mag kaon sa gawas, malakat kmi sa Jollibee gna dala namon siya sa Jollibee ky amo man ng paborito niya nga ano... nga ano restaurant, ay fast food gli*

Despite financial constraints, the speaker and their family choose to spend their resources on dining out rather than eating at home. The specific mention of Jollibee, a fast-food restaurant, indicates a deliberate choice based on their child's preferences. It reflects a prioritization of quality time and creating positive memories, emphasizing the importance of fulfilling their child's desires and making the most of the resources available to them for the benefit of family bonding and enjoyment. This sentiment showcases a resilient and adaptable approach to finding joy and connection within the family despite financial limitations.

P3 stated the following, *parehas sina ng tatlo namon ka bata mahilig na sa 7/11, paghibi na grabe na maghibi hmblan mo lang sila nga maadto sa 7/11 okay na na. magbihis na para madkadto nata sa 7/11. Wala na na ga dugang pa di na na maghibi daw amo ng ila nga ano.*

This insight reflects the significance of 7/11 as a source of joy and comfort for the children and highlights the family's adaptability in incorporating such experiences into their daily lives. The ability to adjust and respond to the diverse needs of their children reflects an adaptive and resilient parenting within the context of their generational characteristics.

Empathetic

Empathetic parents help kids grow positively, while a lack of empathy is often linked to later behavioral issues. Empathy is super important for a child's healthy development, shaping their genuine and creative sense of self. As adults, this self-awareness helps build a strong and lively personality, allowing them to handle life well and form caring relationships (Simonic 2015). Generation Z parents develop empathy as a result of their past encounters and life experiences. These experiences shape their understanding of others' emotions and perspectives, enabling them to connect with their children on a deeper level and respond to their needs with sensitivity and compassion.

The following was stated by P1, *sa pag discipline... ako abi dali lang abi ko mahurt, ng basta ano basta may ara siya ano. Kung ako ginahambalan ko lang na siya kung ano mga possibility nga mga matabo liwat.*

P1's empathetic approach in disciplining their children involves steering away from harsh methods and, instead, prioritizing effective communication. This comprehensive strategy reflects a deep understanding of the child's emotions and perspective. By choosing communication over strict discipline, the parent actively engages with the child's feelings, emphasizing empathy in their parenting

Meanwhile, in the case of P2, “*sa akon nga nag dako nga waay sang parent noh ng kumbaga naga buo ka sang relationship mo saimo nga bata*”

The participants' absence of parental figures has made them more empathetic toward their own children, as they aim to ensure their children do not experience a sense of deficiency in parental love.

P3 also stated the following, *ang bata maski layo sila wala namon na feel nga...layo ang ila feelings sa amon pag abot na sa ila pero ginapangita nila gyapon kami*

This statement showcases empathy in the parents as they recognize and respond to the emotional needs of their child. Despite being away to their child, the parents are attuned to the child’s feelings of longing and actively seek to maintain a connection.

Positive psychology emphasizes the importance of cultivating positive emotions and relationships, and the parents' empathetic actions contribute to a nurturing and supportive family environment. This, in turn, promotes the children's well-being and positive psychological growth, emphasizing the interconnectedness of empathy and positive outcomes in the family

SOP 2: The challenges of Generation Z parents in parenting their Generation Alpha child

The presented table illustrates the challenges being faced by Generation Z parents’ in parenting their Generation Alpha children. Notably there are several challenges faced in order to raise a Generation Alpha child.

Table 2. *Thematic analysis of the challenges of Generation Z parents in parenting their Generation Alpha child*

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme
<i>Participant 1</i> <i>Father: kung mag interact kami, gina... malingaw man abi siya sa cellphone (dad). Di gid abi siya maiwasan.</i>	When spending time with the child usage of the device cannot be avoided	Screen Discipline
<i>Mother: so kung ddto gid abi siya selpon man lang abi siya, selpon lang siya nga selpon.</i>	Child keeps using the cellphone.	Guidance discipline and
<i>Mother: dahil indi gid maiwasan nga ng daw gina hampak niya, asta masakitan ka as a mother masakitan ka gid na gina amo na bata mo pero daw tama man nga kis a gina disiplin gd nga amo sato.</i>	Hurting the child to be disciplined cannot be avoided.	Connection
<i>Mother: ang akon nga challenge, sa akon nga part budlay gid kay syempre kay gaschool ko tapos full time mom ko</i>	Having a hard time balancing life as a student and as a parent.	Economic Hardship
<i>Mother: gina challenge ko na dapat gina tudluan ko na ang mga bata ko nga dapat respetohon gid ko, kay sadto gin try ko man na nga daw gina sabat sabat ko lang, amo akon challenge subong sa mga bata.</i>	Attempting to instill respect for her in her child.	
<i>Mother: Nabatyagan na namon ang kakapoy, kapoy gali damo kapa maagyan nga sakit, maluoy ka sa bata niyo kung gamasakit. Tapos Kung magmasakit sila grabe gali ang inyo pulaw, grabe inyo sacrifice kung may bata kana</i>	Felt the pain and tiredness of sacrificing oneself for the welfare of their child.	
<i>Father: kis a malowbat naman na ti amo na wala na didto nan ga time dira na na sya magdinungol kay patay ang cellphone kag lowbat amo na</i>	Knew what it was like to be hurt and worn out from sacrificing oneself for their child's well-being.	
<i>Mother: So, siya abi kay tutok man siya sa ano sa gaming ti gusto niya mag games. Ti ako, ako nalang didto man ano bantay.</i>	When the gadget's battery is low, the child throws tantrums.	
<i>Mother: daw nalayo na sila sa amon kay mas malingaw abi sila didto. Mas ginapili niya na tong iya nga pinsan kaysa sa amon kay syempre didto siya happy na mo kay kung didto ab isa amon kay daw wala siya kayo friend sa amon.</i>	Because the spouse is preoccupied with gaming, the mother will look after the child.	
<i>Father: Oo nalingaw siya, kag sa amon abi wala siya kaayo ginapagawas.</i>	The parents believe that their child's feelings are drifting away from them as a result of their child's playmates.	
<i>Mother: Ti hindi siya makasalamoha sa mga iban na tao. Tapos hindi siya ano subong sang mahuyaon nga bata sadto abi hndi siya mag interact</i>	Because of their child's timid nature, the parents are anxious about how they can connect socially with others.	

Participant 2

Mother: subong ga ... medjo ga struggle lang sa ano sa... lalo na sa attitude niya (bata) nga ga dako na siya.

Struggling on dealing with the child's attitude

Father: kung sa disiplina ga pati man siya dayun... kung kisa hindi siya ma control kay kung gusto niya, gusto niya gid...

The child can have uncontrollable tantrums occasionally.

Mother: bago kami magpanyapon kwaon na na saiya, pero hagadon mo... may mga times gd nga gna hagad siya mag parizal, hindi gd siya ya mag upod

When attempting to urge the child to walk around—since they are more interested in the device—they refuse to go

Father: dira lang na siya mag higda kg mag lantaw sa tablet niya

The child is copying behaviours or attitudes after what they see on the screen.

Mother: at some point may ara gd siya sang mga ano na observe ko subong nga mga batasan nga halin sa gadget

Thinking back to both the current and previous parenting practices.

Father: kg isa pa ang mga bata subong ga dako, lain dati nga mga nga nahadlok sa ginikanan subong lain na abi subong ang pamalakad sang mga kabataan ky gamay lang nga may Makita nga kwan... sa tanan na bata sa school, ky mahimo nila

The child is imitating the mannerisms or dispositions of other kids that they have witnessed.

Mother: ma ano pa gd siya ky sa skwelahan daan ky may ara nga Makita niya mo nga may mga bata didto nga gabato sa parents nang ga tantrums bala hw, ma ano niya sa sarili niya...

Experiencing difficulty adjusting to the child's new attitudes.

Mother: ang challenges siguro nga na encounter ko saiya ky, lalo na pag ang times nga may batasan siya nabago nga maipakita saamon, like halimbawa suguon siya mag kaon na... mang hindi bala siya hw, "hindi ko!" mag amo na siya, like dw... ako abi as early nga parent wala gd ko nag expect nga may magyan, ma experience namon nib a, ma experience ko ni ti syempre wala gid ko kaayo sang knowledge kung paano ko siya i... paano ko siya disiplinahan.

The mother did not have much experience disciplining her child because she was an early mother.

Thinking back on how current and past parenting differ.

Mother: kung ako lang ha, kung ako lg, iba abi sa dati, kay dati abi butngan lang ta sang pinggan ni nanay ta sa lamesa makaon dun, subong abi damo pa sang kwan... damo pa sang arte ba... amo na ng challenge

Prefers to eat with the device at the side.

Having a hard time in teaching her because of her behavior

Mother: gusto niya mag kaon, mag tablet siya mo... amo ng gusto niya... gusto niya tablet gd habang ga kaon ti dira gd kami na budlayan saiya subng, nabudlayan gd kami mag ano saiya ky may mga batasan na gd siya nga dw mag bato.

Because the child can't poop without a diaper, the parents are struggling financially.

Father: ang subong nga na kwan ko saiya, ga dako siya, gasto gyapon siya sa diaper... hindi siya abi mamos-on (kung wala diaper).

Struggling in keeping in check on the health of their child

Mother: hindi abi siya mag poops nga wala diaper, na pa hospital, na pa ano namon sa doctor ba, tung last niya sa hospital naexplain na sa doctor wala gyapon, may bulong pa nga gn pabakal saamon...

The child's attitude is getting worse as the child grows older.

Struggling on how to be a parent to their child because of being a first time parent.

Father: Sbnng nga ga dako siya... batasan niya gd.

Sometimes the child would throw a tantrum and the

Mother: first time parent ko mo, first baby ko siya amo bala na hw... syempre ga struggle gd ko kung paano... kumbaga na stress ko... may times gd nga mastress gd ko... ky ng sa pasaway niya gani tig-a tig-a na siya ulo... ng hindi na siya... kesa hindi na na siya mag pati, kanang sawayon mo bala siya ... "hindi ka mag higko dra, hindi ka mag sang mga kalat mo"... wala gd siya ga pamati, pero hindi man all the time na wala siya ga pamati sakon as mama niya.

parent would find it difficult to handle.

The parent is having a hard time in providing the child with diapers.

Father: Financial struggle gd ang sa diaper niya.

Father: ang una namon nga bata gibilin pa namon sa kay lola niya kay kami nagtrabaho kami as a teenager parent bay nagtrabaho kami.

Left the child with their grandmother to work and to provide for their child.

Father: Dasun pa ang kamingaw mo sa iya. Daw sa kasan o daw makibot ka nga dako na bata ta daw amo na mangayo mamakal gatas ang lola niya tapos mapadala ka man.

shocked by their child's development because they weren't present to witness it.

Mother: Financial gid financially gastruggle gid kami bakaal sang gatas mangita sang ano. Pero karon mga bayad sa eskwelahan.

Financially struggling on providing the basic needs of their child.

Father: sa una, magbugtaw aga cocomelon, bugtaw aga cocomelon tanaw.

The youngster asks to view a youtube video on the gadget as soon as they wake up.

Mother: ga away sila gaaway gid mag away kami (reason: gadget).

Arguments emerged because of the usage of gadgets.

Father: Tapos bago magtulog mag selpon gid

Before bedtime the child asks to use the device.

Screen-Time Discipline

Generation Z was the first generation born into a globally connected world and therefore “live and breathe” technology. Generation Z also uses social media to communicate with their family and friends to share what is happening to them on a real-time basis (Olipas, 2022). As a result, the lives of Gen Z parents are connected with technology, and they grow up in learning and adapting and integrating the use of technology in their lives. Screen time is the amount of time spent on electronic media, such as playing video games on consoles, watching TV or movies, or using computers, laptops, smartphones, or other portable electronics (Screen Time and Children: MedlinePlus Medical Encyclopedia, 2020). Gen Alpha children now play and interact with and bond with their parents in different ways because of technology. Younger kids use phones and other devices for extended periods of time, which can be both good and bad for their lives.

P1 and his partner stated the following, *kung mag interact kami, gina... malingaw man abi siya sa cellphone. Di gid abi siya maiwasan., so kung ddo gid abi siya selpon man lang abi siya, selpon lang siya nga selpon.*

Establishing and enforcing suitable screen time limitations is a challenging task, as both parents and children become ensnared in a digital web that can have adverse effects on mental and physical health as well as the overall comfort in a household.

P2 stated this, *gusto niya mag kaon, mag tablet siya mo... amo ng gusto niya... gusto niya tablet gd habang ga kaon ti dira gd kami na budlayan saiya subng, nabudlayan gd kami mag ano sa iya kay may mga batasan na gd siya nga dw mag bato.*

This illustrates the parents' difficulties in regulating screen usage during the child's meals, as well as the difficulty in redirecting the child's attention due to their child's habits as well as child's behaviour.

P3 adds to the conversation by saying the following, *sa gadget karon ang ari (bunso) daw indi na gid man siya, magbugtaw aga cocomelon, bugtaw aga cocomelon tanaw. ga away sila gaaway gid mag away kami. Tapos bago magtulog mag selpon gid.*

This shows the usage of cellphones became constant wherein the child always looks for the cellphone before bedtime. These accounts demonstrate the complexities that parents face when it comes to handling screen time discipline. Generation Z parents discussed the difficulties they experienced with screen time discipline, reflecting on the worries of many parents who have integrated technology in their daily lives. Parents and kids alike are giving in to the attraction of continual connectedness as smartphones, tablets, and other

digital devices become ingrained in daily life. Parent Development theory offers a useful perspective for analyzing the difficulties parents have in controlling their Generation Alpha children's screen time. According to the idea advanced in the parent development theory, parents go through different developmental phases and modify their parenting approaches to suit the rapidly evolving cultural, societal, and technical context. Many elements of Parent Development theory are clear when discussing Generation Alpha's screen time discipline.

The testimonies shed light on the difficulties parents encounter when navigating a digital environment that differs greatly from their own upbringing. Gen Z parents of Generation Alpha live in a society where technology is pervasively used in day-to-day activities. This is consistent with the idea in Parent Development theory that parenting practices evolve with each generation in response to the particular difficulties brought about by societal shifts. The challenge of enforcing screen time discipline highlights the necessity for parents to adapt their approaches to the digital age.

Connection

One of the most important aspects of parenting is the bond between parents and children. This is an essential component of parenting that has a big impact on the growth and wellbeing of their child/children. It shapes their relationships with others, their behavior, and their communication and emotional stability. The parent-child relationship can be difficult due to a variety of issues, including modern lifestyles. Because most of the Gen Z parents are students, working students or unemployed or stop schooling to find work to provide for their family. Work responsibilities, hobbies, and other duties can limit parents' time with their children, reducing the quality of their relationship.

As P1 states, *“So, siya abi kay tutok man siya sa ano sa gaming ti gusto niya mag games. Ti ako, ako nalang didto man ano bantay.”*

The account shows that her husband is focused on his hobby which is gaming. While her husband plays games, she is the one who takes care of, plays with and interacts more with their child.

“daw nalayo na sila sa amon kay mas malingaw abi sila didto. Mas ginapili niya na tong iya nga pinsan kaysa sa amon kay syempre didto siya happy na mo kay kung didto ab isa amon kay daw wala siya kayo friend sa amon.”

This statement illustrates what the parents feel towards their child's estrangement towards them preferring their playmates over them. As parents she feels happy as her child makes friends and enjoys childhood but she is still concerned about their child's feelings in their relationship.

P3 stated, *“Ang una namon nga bata gibilin pa namon sa kay lola niya kay kami nagtrabaho kami as a teenager parent bay nagtrabaho kami,”*

They also state that, *“Dasun pa ang kamingaw mo sa iya. Daw sa kasan o daw makibot ka nga dako na bata ta”*

Over time, parents frequently experience a shock when witnessing their child's growth and realizing how long they have been apart from them. These scenarios can generate a sense of distance between parents and children, as the Gen Alpha children may feel neglected or prefer to be with others who are more available. In addition, cultural influences and peer interactions can have an impact on the parent-child relationship, as youngsters may seek approval and acceptance from their friends or relatives rather than their parents. All of these factors can present issues in maintaining a strong and healthy relationship between parent and their children. This can be connected to Social Relational Theory where interpersonal relationships particularly in the family have considerable impact on the development and behavior on their children. Children today may seek relationships beyond the family resulting in weakening their parent-child relationship.

Guidance and Discipline

The parents of Generation Alpha employ discipline strategies like logical consequences and boundaries. They tend to encourage their children to reflect on their actions and explain the consequences of their actions. Meanwhile, the previous generations rely more on a physical approach to their discipline like spanking or other physical punishments. In terms of guidance, Gen Z parents' approach is more on open communication, conversations and sharing their thoughts. In the previous generation of parents, they tend to have an authoritative approach and choose obedience rather than communication. Guidance and discipline toward appropriate conduct are the duties for any parent who provides care for children. It takes a careful balance to establish limits and create a supportive atmosphere while enforcing guidance and punishment in children

P1 stated the following, dahil indi gid maiwasan nga ng daw gina hampak niya, asta masakitan ka as a mother masakitan ka gid na gina amo na bata mo pero daw tama man nga kis a gina disiplina gd nga amo sato, gina challenge ko na dapat gina tudluan ko na ang mga bata ko nga dapat respetohon gid ko, kay sadto gin try ko man na nga daw gina sabat sabat ko lang, amo akon challenge subong sa mga bata.

P1 highlighted the emotional challenges that come with disciplining a child. She acknowledged the difficulty of witnessing her child's disobedience, emphasizing the emotional toll it takes on a mother while recognizing the necessity of disciplining the child.

P2 states the following, *ang challenges siguro nga na encounter ko saiya ky, lalo na pag ang times nga may batasan siya nabago nga*

maipakita saamon, like halimbawa suguon siya mag kaon na... mang hindi bala siya hw, "hindi ko!" mag amo na siya, like dw...

P2 also stated this, *ma ano pa gd siya ky saskwelahan daan ky may ara nga Makita niya mo nga may mga bata didto nga gabato sa parents nang ga tantrums bala hw, ma ano niya sa sarili niya...*

P2 provided insights into the struggles of discipline, particularly in managing his child's attitude and evolving behaviours.

P2 stated the following, *first time parent ko mo, first baby ko siya amo bala na hw... syempre ga struggle gd ko kung paano...kumbaga na stress ko... may times gd nga mastress gd ko... ky ng sa pasaway niya gani tig-a tig-a na siya ulo... ng hindi na siya... kesa hindi na na siya mag pati, kanang sawayon mo bala siya ... "hindi ka mag higko dra, hindi ka mag sang mga kalat mo" wala gd siya ga pamati, pero hindi man all the time na wala siya gapamati sakon as mama niya.*

This statement revealed the difficulties a first-time parent faces when managing the anxiety that comes with the responsibility of teaching self-discipline to a child and managing the child's behaviour. The fact that not all forms of discipline will work right away highlights how difficult it can be to help children develop acceptable behaviour. This can be connected to the theory of Parent Development, which proposes that people create and adapt their parenting perspectives through time. The theory suggests that discipline and guidance of parents evolve through various stages of development as they raise their children. Some factors that lead to this development is the parents upbringing, background, personal experiences of one another and time.

Economic Hardship

Before being parents, Generation Z are mostly students and jobless in which they are relying on their parents with expenses. After becoming parents the financial burden on Gen Z's are growing in which they take responsibility and find jobs to provide for their family. Numerous financial challenges that first-time Gen Z parents encounter have a significant influence on both their own lives and the well-being of their kids. These struggles are frequently linked to the difficulties of striking a balance between meeting their children's educational needs and basic necessities.

According to P2, *"Financial struggle gd ang sa diaper niya," which emphasizes the difficulties in affording even necessities like diapers and the harsh reality of financial hardship.*

Similarly, P3's expresses economic struggle, *"Financial gid financially gastruggle gid kami bakal sang gatas mangita sang ano. Pero karon mga bayad sa eskwelahan,"* which delves deeper into the complex financial struggle of parents, revealing the ongoing struggles to procure not only the basics like milk but also to meet the financial demands of their child's education.

The additional insight from P3, *"Ang una namon ng bata gibilin pa namon sa kay lola niya kay kami nagtrabaho kami as a teenager parent bay nagtrabaho kami,"* highlights the difficult decision to entrust their first child to a grandparent while working as a teenage parents and further highlights the sacrifices made to navigate financial constraints. Together, these testimonies provide a moving portrait of the complex difficulties parents encounter, highlighting the interdependence of financial hardships and the extreme measures parents take to guarantee their children's welfare and education.

SOP 3: The Coping Strategies of Generation Z parents in parenting their Generation Alpha child

In the exploration of coping strategies employed by Generation Z parents in the parenting of Generation Alpha children, several coping strategies emerged upon analysis which help them in parenting their Generation Alpha children.

Table 3. *Thematic analysis of Coping Strategies of Generation Z parents in parenting their Generation Alpha child*

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme
Participant 1 FATHER: <i>"ako, lapit lang man abi balay namon sa pihak kanto, gapangita gid ko sang way para maglakat ddto para divert ang iya nga ginapokusan nga ginaka abalahan sa balay. (referring to cellphone)"</i>	Finding way to divert the attention of child from gadget	Physical Interaction
MOTHER: <i>"pag may ara kami sang mga dako dako nga problema nga... mag pray gid kami, always kami, kis a abi devotional kami nga tao nga magpamilya so amo na kis a maisip ko man nga dako bulig sa pagpray sa Ginoo kay daw ginabuligan niya ang imo nga sitwasyon nga maging gaan ba nga amo na ba nga kayahon ko as a mother kay syempre gin face ko ning situation ngani, magkwan ka gid labanan mo gid."</i>	Prayer as source of strength Belief in power of prayer Being strong	Prayer and optimism Time Management Parental Adaptation Responsible parenthood

<p>FATHER: “Magpakatatag, don’t give up, kay gi sudlan namon ni mo, amo na always gid namon gina, dalawa kami ga isturyahanay kami (gin sudlan namon ni) Kaya tani ah siguro gin hatag lang ni ni Lord nga challenge para ipakita saaton nga kung ano gid ta ka tibay duwa. Magpakakatag gid ba, always gid namon gina sink in sa amon isip”</p>	<p>Motivating each other Always putting in mind to be resilient</p>
<p>FATHER: “Tong pareha sa gihambal ko, ginalagaw namon sila sa pihak kag ginahampang “</p>	<p>Taking children for a walk Engaging with relatives</p>
<p>MOTHER: “Tapos ma bonding gid na sila sang pinsan niya amo ng una gid namon nga ginahimo”</p>	<p>Avoiding technology through engaging with relatives</p>
<p>FATHER: “Amo to daw dako man siya nga bulig nga daw gipalikaw namon siya sa technology kay daw mas ginapili niya na didto sa pinsan niya nga mag stay”</p>	<p>Being responsible as part of parental obligation</p>
<p>FATHER: “ang responsibilidad, ang responsibilidad ko gid bilang ama ang nag kwan sa akon.”</p>	<p>Adjusting schedule to attend the needs of the child</p>
<p>FATHER: “Tong dati abi kay hindi ko sila matutokan kay day class paman ko dati, ti subong nag night class ko para sa aga ma kwan ko gid sila maano ko gid bilang ama magampanan ko ang responsibilidad para mas mag improve kag nag improve gid ang akon nga fatherhood.”</p>	<p>Adjusting schedule to attend the needs of the child</p>
<p>PARTICIPANT 2</p>	
<p>MOTHER: “kaya ang style ko para hindi mag ano mag sigi ka gadget amo na gna hatag ko saiya (referring to learning activities: drawing books, etc). pero kung si papa niya ara, rizal park gd na sila ky damo ddo bata”</p>	<p>Providing educational materials to divert the attention from gadget Engaging with other children</p>
<p>MOTHER: “ang gina himo ko na lang kay... ulo-ulohan ko lang gd siya, angga anggaon ko lang gd siya, lambing lambingon ko siya ky para lang bala mag pati siya sakon haw kay kung gulpi gulpihon ko siya abi nga istorya or singhalan hindi gd tana siya ya, hindi mo gd siya ma force amo gd abi na ng mga bata sbng kay dw mga bata ta abi sbng kailangan attention gd”</p>	<p>Providing affectionate environment Give attention to the child Gentle way of communicating to the child</p>
<p>MOTHER: “as a parent ng labaoon mo gd ang pasensya mo kag pag intindi ky bata pa siya mo... like amo ng obligasyon mo as a parent ky ikaw ang... kumbaga I guide mo siya, guidance gd ang... mabulig sa bata mo.”</p>	<p>Avoiding hurtful words Extending patience Giving the child’s wants</p>

MOTHER: “gina storya ko siya sa pahinay lang”

MOTHER: “paano ko siya eh dw kumbaga ang disiplina ko saiya hinay hinay mo... hindi bala sinang torture or words... sakit na nga words, hindi ... pero kay ang pag disiplina ko abi saiya kay patience gd abi kung wala”

FATHER: “oo sa akon ky ako ang financial provider gd... gina pagustohan gd siya... wala gd siya makwan sakon ky ti kung ano gusto niya... basta may ara lang... basta bata pa, hatag ah.”

MOTHER: “as a nanay ano ang struggle, gina cope up ko gd, gina kaya ko, ga set gd ko sang goals kahit sa every month lang na, biskan sa monthly bills namon ako gd ng tig set sng goal”

FATHER: “dira gd ko na ningkamot trabaho para saiya, lain gd kung... dati nga sultero ka pa nga may... subong nga may pamilyado na nga dapat bakas gd para sa future niya”

PARTICIPANT 3

BOTH: “Mag ipon, maging positive.

FATHER: mag ipon kung mag abot ang sweldo, mauli kaw magkadto sa bata mo madala sang iya pagkaon”

FATHER: “Manghulam para makauli lang man ka para maupod lang siya. Amo lang nang budlay kay layo kami sang una.”

FATHER: “naguli kami ila parents happy na sila nga nag uli kami didto nga nag updanay kami ddto happy sila kag may dala kami nga pasalubong para sa ila sang una, madala kami nga mga gatas pagkaon gummies mga amo na happy na sila daw sa amo na nga mga edad di pa nila feel ang problema basta ano lang enjoy”

MOTHER: “kis a gina akigan ko na sila kis a gasunggod gid na sila saakon amo nga gina lambing ko naman na sila tapos kung indi ko kaya ginapasa ko gid sa iya, siya gid abi (referring to father).”

MOTHER: “makit’an mo gid abi sa bata kung pag apply mo sina nga amo gali na kung kigan mo sya tapos lainon mo naman imo nga strategy sa pagpadako mo sa iya nga pag akig mo sa iya pagsunog sina dapat lambingon mo siya. Ihatag mo gusto niya para indi siya magdumot sa imo.”

FATHER: “kung feel ko nga daw indi man lng mahatag ka mama niya maadto sakon , ihatag ko gid na ang gusto nila amo gd na basta kung in case nga... incase nga amo na gusto nila”

MOTHER: “ga depende kami sa kung ano response sang bata sa amon”

MOTHER: “ginabawalan tung sa subang namon na ano gid to siya sa gadget natutok pero sa karon 1hour 1hour lang ginabawalan man gyapon sila.”

Setting goal as part of coping mechanism

Work hard and set priorities

Be positive and save money for the needs of children

Borrowing money to be with children

Visiting the children

Providing needs of children

Providing safe environment for the child

Observing child’s reaction to discipline

Adjusting to child’s behavior

Helping one another

Adjusting to child’s behavioral response

Imposing limited screen time

Diverting child’s attention from gadget

Imposing limited screen time

Presenting situation to the child

FATHER: “Ti kay kwaon mn na namon ang gadget syempre makadto na siya sa gwas para maghampang pero kung ihatag mo ang gadget di na gid siya maggawas.”

MOTHER: “kung ako sa gabi patan’awon ko man na siya, alas dyes lang asta ha, ok mang, matulog nako mang amo na sabat niya.”

Adjusting to child’s behavioral response

Give enough time phasing to the child to process

FATHER: “Sa akon lain nman magadget siya da mahulam ko dada may ichat ko matest ko ihatag niya tapos paghatag niya ato namn na siya sa gawas. Ato na na siya sa gawas gaan mo lang dyes makadto na siya sa tindahan bakal amo na kendi mga gummies pagkaon amo na. tapos pag abot ni (bunso) kwarta kwarta.”

Negotiating and giving child phase to adjust

FATHER: “mapati nalang pero hindi mo lang pagbiglaon nga..”

MOTHER: “hinay hinayon mo lang isgturya ba”

FATHER: “Halimbawa mahamabal na siya nga indi ko magsugot, indi lang anay kay mahibi man na taod2 lang ha, akon namn ha ako namn pagtapos, pagtapos niya bantayan mo namn pagtapos niya kay kwaon mo namn. Ako namn.”

Physical Social Interaction

Generation Z parents recognize the importance of broader family connections in the upbringing of their Generation Alpha child. Physical activity interventions with children created a sense of community and encouraged them to be more active which diverts their attention from the use of technology (Liu, Y., Zhang Hong-xue, & Xu, R., 2023). By encouraging physical interaction with cousins, generation Z parents not only provide a social outlet but also help the child to avoid too much engagement with gadget and technology.

P1 stated the following, *ako, lapit lang man abi balay namon sa pihak kanto, gapangita gid ko sang way para maglakat ddo para divert ang iya nga ginapokusan nga ginaka abalahan sa balay. (referring to cellphone), Amo to daw dako man siya nga bulig nga daw gipalikaw namon siya sa technology kay daw mas ginapili niya na didto sa pinsan niya nga mag stay, Tong pareha sa gihambal ko, ginalagaw namon sila sa pihak kag ginahampang, Tapos ma bonding gid na sila sang pinsan niya amo ng una gid namon nga ginahimo, Amo to daw dako man siya nga bulig nga daw gipalikaw namon siya sa technology kay daw mas ginapili niya na didto sa pinsan niya nga mag stay*

P2 stated the following, *kaya ang style ko para hindi mag ano mag sigi ka gadget amo na gna hatag ko saiya (referring to learning activities: drawing books, etc.), pero kung si papa niya ara, rizal park gd na sila ky damo ddo bata*

Allowing Generation Alpha children to socially engage with the community shows the importance of broader connection with the society in upbringing them. Generation Z parents recognizes that there is a need to balance with the use of technology and harnessing its benefits because of societal shift. This means that physical social interaction among children in the face of evolving parenting challenges in this digital age is one way of Generation Z parents to shape the Generation Alpha children.

As part of being a child in this age, Generation Z parents could not deny the fact that use of technology allows their children advancement in learning such as learning phonetics and other educational activities that allows them to develop their mental ability.

This signifies that in being a Generation Z parent, there is a need to give the Generation Alpha children a balance of physical interaction and use of technology that affects their children’s cognitive development. Unstructured play, engagement with physical objects, and face-to-face interactions stimulate different areas of the brain, promoting creativity, imagination, and critical thinking skills. Establishing healthy screen time habits from an early age is essential for preventing issues like digital addiction and ensuring that children learn to manage their time effectively. Balancing technology use also encourages parental involvement, as parents can actively guide and monitor their children's activities. This coping strategy is tied with Social Relational theory where parents and children are part of the society and they need to be involved in the society in order for them to connect and behave within the society for their development as a human being.

Prayer and Optimism

With the emergence of different challenges in raising a Generation Alpha child, P1 encapsulates the unwavering commitment to prayer and being optimistic as an integral part of their response to parenting difficulties, *“pag may ara kami sang mga dako dako nga problema*

nga... mag pray gid kami, always kami, kis a abi devotional kami nga tao nga magpamilya so amo na kis a maisip ko man nga dako bulig sa pagpray sa Ginoo kay daw ginabuligan niya ang imo nga sitwasyon nga maging gaan ba nga amo na ba nga kayahon ko as a mother kay syempre gin face ko ning situation ngani, magkwan ka gid labanan mo gid."

This reliance on prayer is not merely a ritual but rather a continuous source of strength and guidance. Prayer was used as a coping skill when an individual had a problem to have spiritual connection, asking religious forgiveness, and collaborative religious coping (Smith, J. 2018). It highlights the Generation Z parents' perception of prayer as a means to alleviate the weight of their parenting challenges. It signifies a spiritual connection that provides comfort and eases the burdens inherent in raising the Generation Alpha.

Moreover, the view that challenges are presented by a higher power as opportunities for personal growth is evident in the statement of P1, "*Siguro ginhatag lang ni Lord nga challenge para ipakita sa aton nga kung ano gid ta ka tibay duwa."*

This perspective views the challenges not as obstacles but as intentional opportunities for them as generation z parents to showcase their resilience and inner strength. The reliance on prayer is not a one-time event but a continuous practice, indicating an ongoing relationship with spirituality. This generation of parents is having a foundation that helps them cope with the ever- evolving nature of parenting in the digital age.

Prayer serves as a consistent pillar of support for Generation Z parents raising a Generation Alpha child where it can foster a sense of connection, and it develops a sense of optimism to the individual to view positivity within the struggle in life (Rogers, K. 2020). It serves as a psychological benefit of generation z parents through prayer that reflects a resilient mindset that views challenges as avenues for their personal and spiritual growth, fostering a positive and empowered parental experience.

Time Management

The awareness of the need to manage time effectively to fulfill both educational and parenting duties aims for personal and familial improvement to attend to the needs of the children. The families with kids might face more problems because of the lack of planning ability of kids on parental responsibilities alongside their planning of professional and personal life (Emadi, 2018).

P1 stated the following, *Tong dati abi kay hindi ko sila matutokan kay day class paman ko dati, ti subong nag night class ko para sa aga ma kwan ko gid sila maano ko gid bilang ama magampanan ko ang responsibilidad para mas mag improve kag nag improve gid ang akon nga fatherhood.*

Since they have the struggle in attending to the needs of their children due to commitment constraints, there is a need to shift from day classes to night classes. It reflects a deliberate effort to prioritize and fulfil the responsibilities as a parent. The decision to attend night classes, despite the potential challenges, underscores the commitment to improve parenting skills. The adjustment on schedule demonstrates a keen understanding of the importance of time management in balancing academic pursuits with the responsibilities of being a parent.

Allocating time is essential in navigating the responsibilities associated with raising the Generation Alpha children. It is influenced by the Parent Development Theory that underscores the idea that generation z parents actively seek opportunities for personal and familial improvement, adapting their schedules to align with the evolving needs of their children. This generation of parents undergo continuous growth and adaptation to meet the changing demands of their roles, and effective time management is a fundamental aspect of this developmental process. By allocating time wisely, parents not only address the immediate needs of their children but also set an example for effective planning and organization, contributing to the development of their children.

Parental Adaptation

The concept of parental adaptation is vividly expressed in participants' statements, highlighting the nuanced and thoughtful approach in raising an alpha child. Having patience and understanding is evident in parenting as a coping strategy. Generation Z parents' chose to approach situations with a calm demeanor, gently and affectionately attending to their child's needs, which reflects a conscious decision to guide rather than impose.

P2 stated the following, *ang gina himo ko na lang kay... ulo-ulohan ko lang gd siya, angga anggaon ko lang gd siya, lambing lambingon ko siya ky para lang bala mag pati siya sakon haw, way nga paano ko siya eh dw kumbaga ang disiplina ko saiya hinay-hinay mo... hindi bala sinang torture or words... sakit na nga words, hindi ... pero kay ang pag disiplina ko abi saiya kay patience gd abi*

These statements underscore the importance of building trust through a nurturing and patient demeanor. By extending patience it can help regulate emotion, allowing parents to stay calm, make decisions and persist through difficulties (Linz, R. & Schnitker, S. 2023)

Moreover, the recognition of the need for attention in children aligns with the understanding that they, like all individuals, require emotional connection and guidance. The acknowledgement that forceful approaches may not be effective resonates with a contemporary parenting philosophy that emphasizes communication, empathy, and understanding.

P2 stated the following, *Kay kung gulpi gulpihon ko siya abi nga istorya or singhalan hindi gd tana siya ya, hindi mo gd siya ma force amo gd abi na ng mga bata sbng kay dw mga bata ta abi sbng kailangan attention gd."* and "*way nga paano ko siya eh dw kumbaga*

ang disiplina ko sa iya hinay-hinay mo... hindi bala sinang torture or words... sakit na nga words, hindi ... pero kay ang pag disiplina ko abi sa iya kay patience gd abi"

This statement presents that a gentle way of disciplining is important to cope with generation alpha children's behavior. The Generation Z parents' belief that parenthood comes with the responsibility and obligation to guide your child aligns with the idea that being a parent involves more than just providing physical care, but encompasses emotional support, understanding, and fostering growth. Participant 3 stated, "*Amo ng obligasyon mo as a parent ky ikaw ang... kumbaga I guide mo siya, guidance gd ang... mabulig sa bata mo*" which encapsulates the sense of duty and nurturing that characterizes their parenting style.

Moreover, P3 observes children's behavior and the children's reaction to their way of disciplining, "*Makit'an mo gid abi sa bata kung pag apply mo sina nga amo gali na kung kigan mo sya tapos lainon mo naman imo nga strategy sa pagpadako mo sa iya nga pag akig mo sa iya pagsunod sina dapat lambingon mo siya, ga depende kami sa kung ano response sang bata sa amon.*"

Catering to what the Generation Alpha child wants is also evident in this study wherein P3 stated that, "*Ihatag mo gusto niya para indi siya magdumot sa imo*".

This reflects a responsive and adaptable parenting style that shows the importance of adjusting to the children in order to foster a positive and supportive environment. Their approach in coping with the challenges aligns with Positive Psychology theory and Parent Developmental theory which give emphasis on patience, understanding, empathy and gentle way of disciplining the Generation Alpha children which contributes to the positive emotional well-being of a child.

Responsible Parenthood

As a parent they are demonstrating their deep commitment in fulfilling their child's needs. Being able to recognize the child's needs and wants and being able to support them in achieving these things are important. Responsible parenthood also has to do with parents aiding their children to become happy, responsible adults (Valledor, M. 2023).

Generation Z parents provide a generous and nurturing approach in coping amidst financial struggles as stated by P2, "*oo sa akon ky ako ang financial provider gd... gina pagustohan gd siya... wala gd siya makwan sakon ky ti kung ano gusto niya... basta may ara lang... basta bata pa, hatag ah.*"

To provide for the needs of the children they emphasize the need for striving hard for employment to support the children. They are willing to give up the single life that they have in order to fulfil their parental responsibility.

As stated by P2, "*Dira gd ko na ningkamot trabaho para sa iya, lain gd kung... dati nga sultero ka pa nga may... subong nga may pamilyado na nga dapat bakas gd para sa future niya, Mag ipon, maging positive. Mag ipon kung mag abot ang sweldo, mauli kaw magkadto sa bata mo madala sang iya pagkaon*

Moreover, as stated in the challenges, Generation Z parents are having difficulty because of multiple commitments. As a result, P3 becomes positive in coping with the challenges in order to fulfil the duty as a parent. Parents are also willing to travel extra mile to aid the loneliness of their children. Indeed, not all children can experience the privilege of growing up in an ideal family environment and this is one of the vital responsibilities in raising a child (Makati Medical Center, 2020)

As stated by P3, "*Manghulam para makauli lang man ka para maupod lang siya., Naga uli kami, ila parents happy na sila nga nag uli kami didto, nga nag updanay kami ddto happy sila kag may dala kami nga pasalubong para sa ila. sang una, madala kami ng mga gatas pagkaon gummies mga amo na happy na sila*

It shows that Generation Z parents have the willingness to sacrifice in order to provide for the children and give significance to the happiness that they could bring to them. Parent Development theory supports these, as they portray responsible parenthood through financial dedication, strategic planning in meeting the children despite the schedule and distance and the effort to provide family time that gives the children a meaningful family experience which shows the willingness to adapt and foster positive development in raising Generation Alpha children.

Conclusions

This study aimed to describe the parenting of Generation Alpha children, the challenges encountered in parenting Generation Alpha children, and coping mechanisms employed on challenges encountered by Generation Z parents.

Describing Parenting of Generation Z parents. Parents in Generation Z employ a variety of discipline strategies, ranging from gentle to harsh. This diversity demonstrates that there are various methods for providing exceptional parenting, each of which takes into account the unique dynamics and style of the family. All parents want the best for their children and to form close relationships with them, despite these variances.

Parenting is approached differently by Generation Alpha parents, who combine empathy, adaptability, and tenderness. According to the findings, parents would sooner softly converse with their children and teach them than take harsh action. These parents place a high value on spending quality time with their children and participating in socializing and bonding activities. Instilling virtues like

awareness and discipline is another important aspect of their parenting; they help their children behave responsibly while simultaneously paying close attention to their wants and needs. The results showed that parents would much rather teach and have a kind conversation with their kids than punish them. These parents think it's important to engage in socializing and bonding activities as well as spend quality time with their kids.

In addition, parents belonging to Generation Alpha are proactive in utilizing resources and adjusting to changing situations in order to give their kids the best possible care. They place a high value on physical activity because they understand how important physical growth and health are.

They emphasize the value of early bonding and learning in the home, and they are committed to building healthy ties with their children in spite of the absence of parental figures. The values of this generation of parents are education and family bonding; they create an atmosphere that is conducive to thoughtful discipline, open communication, and a strong emotional bond within the family. This is consistent with Parent Development Theory, which proposes an evolving parental perspective with the goal of promoting a flexible and positive parent-child dynamic.

Challenges encountered by Generation Alpha parents. Parenting Generation Alpha children presents difficulties for Generation Z parents, such as lack of preparedness for parenthood and financial difficulties. Parents in Generation Z may not have the maturity and life experience necessary to make well-informed decisions on their child's health, education, and general development, which can have a negative impact on their emotional and mental wellbeing. They frequently feel overburdened and compromise their personal wellbeing for the benefit of their child because they struggle to strike a balance between their responsibilities as parents and students.

Moreover, In the current digital era, generation Alpha parents encounter many difficulties, notable among them being screen time management. Integrating technology into parenting presents difficulties including controlling screen time and creating a balance. They struggle with the child's attitude and behavior despite their best efforts to establish discipline and respect; this is made worse by the child's frequent usage of technology. Because of their dependence on technology, children may emulate bad conduct from screens and become uncontrollably irrational when refused access to them, making discipline and guiding difficult.

Additionally, financial struggles add to their burden, such as providing basic needs like diapers and balancing work to support their child. This financial strain impacts their ability to keep up with their child's health needs and education. The absence of parental figures due to work further complicates their parenting journey, leading to feelings of guilt and regret for missing out on crucial moments in their child's development. Despite these challenges, Generation Alpha parents strive to provide the best for their children, even as they navigate the complexities of modern parenting and technological influences.

Due to financial struggles, they are also under pressure in supporting their child and basic necessities such as diapers. This financial burden hinders their ability to meet their child's medical and educational demands. Their parenting approach is made complicated by their own absence as parental figures due to work, which can leave them feeling guilty and regretful about missing out on critical developmental milestones for their child. Despite these challenges, Generation Alpha parents want to offer their children the best life possible while navigating the complexities of modern parenting and the impact of technology.

These insights highlight the importance of a thorough grasp of the unique issues that Generation Alpha parents face, emphasizing the relevance of parental preparedness, financial burden, screentime discipline, and establishing discipline.

Coping mechanisms employed on challenges encountered by Generation Z parents. In coping with the challenges in parenting their Generation Alpha children, parents limit their choices, which allows them to instill their own beliefs and values to their child. Generation Alpha parents recognize the benefits of technology in their life, they can help with learning and engagements in educational activities that helps enhance their mental capacity. Parents also understand the risks of screen time and the importance of balancing screen time to further develop the social development of their children.

They recognize the importance of diverting their children's focus away from electronic devices and toward physical and social activities. To establish a more balanced atmosphere, they take children on walks, engage with family, and encourage connections with other children. These activities not only minimize screen time but also encourage physical and social growth, which is consistent with their belief in the power of prayer and optimism as sources of strength.

Furthermore, Generation Alpha parents place an emphasis on time management and parental adaptation in order to effectively meet their children's needs. They alter their schedules and provide educational materials to redirect their children's attention away from technology, exhibiting responsible parenting. In addition, they foster an affectionate environment by paying attention to their children and conversing calmly. This strategy develops a strong parent-child link and aids in the avoidance of unpleasant remarks, as parents demonstrate patience and give in to their child's needs when appropriate.

Furthermore, Generation Alpha parents demonstrate resilience and a proactive approach to coping with parenting issues. They create objectives, work hard, and prioritize their children's needs, frequently saving or borrowing money to support them. Despite financial difficulties, they make time for their children on a regular basis and provide a safe environment for them. They observe how their children respond to discipline and alter their conduct accordingly, demonstrating a willingness to adapt and learn. Generation Alpha parents try to balance their children's use of technology with other activities by placing a restriction on screen time and negotiating

with them. These coping strategies aligned up with the three theories: positive psychology, social relational theory, and parent development theory. Parent Development Theory highlights how events and personal circumstances shape parenting evolve through time. The parents' adaptive parenting is evident in their attempts to get their children minimize contact with technology and into social and physical activities. Social activities can relate to Social Relational Theory, which emphasizes the significance of parent-child relationships in molding development, and can be related to by engaging in social activities. Parents are building healthy relationships with their children by doing things like going for walks and spending time with family members, which encourage physical and social contact.

Furthermore, the Positive Psychology Theory, which emphasizes the value of developing positive emotions, strengths, and resilience, can be linked to parents who maintain positive relationships with their children. Generation Alpha parents use coping mechanisms such as goal- setting, resilience, and maintaining a positive outlook. This supports the idea in positive psychology theory that resilience and strength-building are key components in fostering well- being.

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